

Educational Restructuring and Inclusive Practices through Digital Learning in India

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Abstract

India has witnessed a remarkable transformation in the field of education through rapid digitalisation, particularly after the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. The sudden shift from traditional classroom teaching to online learning created a new educational paradigm commonly referred to as the “new normal.” Digital education has emerged as a significant tool in ensuring continuity in learning, accessibility, and inclusiveness across different sections of society. The pandemic drastically influenced teaching and learning methodologies worldwide, accelerating the adoption of online education platforms. The present study examines the restructuring of Indian education through digital transformation and examines its appropriateness, sustainability, and effectiveness for future generations.

The paper also traces the evolution of the Indian education system from the Gurukul system to modern digital classrooms, highlighting the role of educational reforms, commissions, and policies in shaping contemporary education, emphasized that modern technology has significantly improved teaching methods, learning outcomes, and student engagement. The study further discusses how digital platforms, learning management systems, webinars, online collaborative learning, and virtual classrooms have transformed educational accessibility and innovation in India. Using systematic analysis and secondary sources such as journal articles, educational websites, government reports, and scholarly literature, this paper critically explores the role of digital education in promoting fairness and justice, especially among marginalized communities. The study identifies that digital learning not only supports educational continuity during crises but also contributes to nation-building and sustainable development. Digital education plays a crucial role in enhancing human resources and preparing societies for the demands of the digital era.

The paper concludes that digitalisation has become an inevitable and transformative force in Indian education, enabling the vision of “Education for All” under Article 21A of the Indian Constitution. Despite challenges such as digital divide, cyber safety concerns, and technological accessibility, India continues to progress towards an inclusive, innovative, and sustainable educational future through digital transformation.

Keywords: Digitalisation, Online Education, New Normal, Educational Transformation, Innovation, Inclusive Learning, India.

Objectives:-

- ✓ The restructuring of education in India through digitalization,

- ✓ The appropriateness and sustainability of online education to the present and the future generation, and
- ✓ To promote fairness and justice in terms of education through online even to the most marginalized sections of the society.

For generation's together people across the world contributed immensely for developing education in their countries. Any country which invest in educating its people, is considered to be the most competitive and progressing. Education reflects on enhancing each and every country in innumerable ways, it focuses more on the aspects of historical, cultural, social, political, and economic development. Education acts as a comprehensive system, its diverse areas are not only related to each other but act together.

Research methodology

Research methodology plays a pivotal role in determining the ways through the anticipation of the study

- Research analysis used in this paper is systematic analysis.
- The information is collected from a diverse resource.
- The reviews usually then were summarized, synthesized, and then critically inspected.
- Data were collected through observation, critical thinking of the researcher on the topic and also other Internet sources, articles and journal references.
- Source for scrutinizing this study was primarily picked from various educational websites, articles done by various researchers, scholars and government websites.

Renovation in Education in the “New Normal”

Post pandemic had made education very challenging. This renovation through digital mode of education is “*a new normal*”(Bozkurt et al., 2020). What does the world love about the new normal? Simply to answer this question, everything about it! Though the new normal is very challenging it is indeed very interesting and people love change for people around the globe. Above all the financial and economical hurdles people learned to sustain, people learned to fight, people learned to adapt and survive. Amongst many challenges educating children and students through different age group became an innovative task. The transition of “*Chalkboard to digital mode*” (Dhawan, 2020) of education was a great challenge for progressing country like India. The post pandemic effects in fact had made people more creative and innovative, it inspires not only students and teachers but people from all age group to investigate, discover, and help them to

practice innumerable tools to be more innovative. Renovation includes trial and error; it initiates young minds to look at problems in different ways and supports in solving them. This unquestionably promotes education since it encourages pupils to approach complex issues from a higher level of reasoning.

CHART-1 -Adapted from “World Economic Forum: The upward Trend in Online Learning” by Johnny Wood

India has come a long way in utilizing technology. After the outburst of Covid-19 and the lockdown then after enabled people to depend on technology for every mean. Engaging children of various age groups through online classes become day to day routine in people life. The above chart clearly explains the usage of digital platforms for educating their children has rapidly increased since the year 2018-2021. Comparatively the contemporary methods in teachings are preferred for the traditional ones. But how was education in the ancient India? And how did it play a significant part in reformulating the current educational system to fit the new normal?

EVOLUTION OF INDIAN EDUCATION

One of the most fascinating things to surely know about is ancient education system in India. To teach the forth coming generations and provide a sustainable growth, the education system was well planned, systematic and organized, it was indeed deep in the roots of society (Altekar, 2009).

It was traced from ancient history, and the kings ruling India immensely contributed for the development of education.

The ages has been categorized into

CHART-2- AGES IN INDIAN EDUCATION

Education system in Ancient India

Gurukul System of learning was predominantly taught during ancient times. Students and teachers were boarding together. They made it to a point to pass on knowledge generations after generations. In fact ancient Indian education is always believed to be very disciplined and well-ordered. Writings were taught in Palm leaves and tree barks, and was recorded in the same. Sages and academics preached most of the teachings verbally. The primary subjects covered in instruction were astrology, religion, philosophy, and combat

. Education system during Medieval India

Through the establishment of schools in the majority of Indian communities, education was broadly disseminated. Madrasas were first established in the 18th century, along with libraries and literary clubs. Universities like Nalanda University, Vikramshila University, Takshashila University, and Ujjain were started during the medieval period. Astronomy, Grammar, Logic, Philosophy, Literature, Law, Medicine, Buddhism, Arthashastra (Politics and Economics), Mathematics, and Logic were taught in both general education and specialist courses as important fields of study. To advance their knowledge, academics began to travel to India from all over the world.

Education system in Modern India

In the 20th century, Lord Macaulay thought that Indians should learn new techniques and contemporary methods, hence he believed that the Indians should retrieve from the old thought process of being traditional and morals. The British East India Company was the first to provide education to modern India, so the study of the English language began. From then to now, India is experiencing renovation in its education system.

Education system-Post independence,

The union government had a lot of control over the education sector soon after India gained independence in 1947. But gradually, as a result of a constitutional amendment in 1976, the federal and state governments collaborated on it.

A Radical restructuring – “The proposal for equal education in the country”

Maulana Abul Kalam Azad, India’s first minister of education structured a strong and consistent central government authority over education. There were commissions established to strengthen the system by the union government to improve education across the nation.

CHART-3- RADICAL RESTRUCTURING

All the above had proposed to update India's educational framework. The government of Jawaharlal Nehru, India's first Prime Minister, adopted the concept of technology and scientific policy. The resolution was taken during the tenure of Nehru government, where the creation of top-notch scientific education institutes, such the - (IITs), was supported by the union government in the year 1961. This did, in fact, lay a solid foundation for technical advancements in education across the nation. The Kothari Commission (1964–1966) produced a report and made recommendations, which Prime Minister Indira Gandhi's administration made public. Equal educational opportunities were suggested in "The First National Policy on Education" of 1968, which advocated for a "radical restructuring" (National Policy on Education 1968) in order to promote economic progress and national integration.

The first national educational policy chose to implement the Indian Constitution's proposal of making education mandatory for all children up to the age of 14 years old. It also covered the qualification of teachers and their specialized training.

In the twenty-first century, various commissions and educational policies had been established. Many suggestions were envisioned and developed by this panel, which were later endorsed and put into action. Providing children with free lunches and free, mandatory schooling till the age of 14 was a successful objective. There were plans to invest 6% of GDP in education, with a concentration on elementary education and other developmental activities.

The appropriateness and sustainability of online education

Thinking creatively and putting forward ideas in novel ways are key components of innovation. Three main processes are involved in innovation: the generation of the concept, its execution, and the results. In terms of education, it necessitates sustainability and inventiveness. It inspires future generations. The modern approaches make extensive use of clever techniques and creative learning. The system of education is being restructured mostly through online schooling. It includes many teaching methods, learning strategies, methodological approaches, and instructional tools that, when used, cause a major shift in teaching and learning that improves students' comprehension of the subjects. Therefore, the goal of creativity in education is to increase learning

effectiveness and/or improve learning quality. In education, the effectiveness of learning is mostly influenced by the knowledge.

Why Modern Teaching Method?

Children nowadays are intelligent, scared, and have recently shown a marked increase in their ability to adapt to new scientific and technological knowledge. A study reveals that 96% of adolescents in OECD (The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) countries have access to digital devices at home, and 83% of young children use digital technologies regularly, this signifies rise in the digital literacy and adaptability among children (OECD, 2025) Science and technological sectors today encompass a much wider range of information. In order to explore unknown ground in a range of businesses, there is a larger need for ingenious and innovative minds. Adopting innovative approaches is the best way to deal with technology and survive in this competitive society. The explosion from Covid19 was highly unpredictable. The ability to completely transform education over the internet has gotten simpler because to the present generation's intelligence.

In the twenty-first century, imaginative and creative minds are essential for the progress of individuals, society, and the nation. Students should develop into

Why modern teaching is the need of the hour?

The focus of education in the future is increasingly on digitalization. Therefore, converting the traditional educational model to a digital one will aid in the nation's overall development. Despite many issues that may first arise, there are numerous approaches to redefine government.

Promotion in terms of fairness and justice in education

To promote fairness and justice in terms of education through online, the following points can be effective.

➤ International Collaboration

For the futuristic and sustainable development collaborative learning is very much necessary. This will aid educators in developing the skills that businesses need.

Collaboration among students requires a skilled method. Collaborative skills will enable the students to create a interactive platform globally and helps them to have an exposure understanding different perspectives thus, enhancing verbal communication, and building their self-esteem. Instilling individual problem-solving abilities would extend learning outside the classroom as a result of this.

➤ **Focusing On Digital Curriculum**

Digital curriculum is more customised and ensures that the teachers focus more on students. Learning Management System and Classroom Management System offers interactive lessons, pre-planned lesson plans, automated assessments, printable worksheets, ready-made presentations, and much more.

➤ **Creating Modern Classrooms**

Modern classrooms with digital equipment will be more fascinating and fun loving for the students. This will increase the thirst for education. Exploring the technical platforms with contemporary methodologies would enable easy learning and perfect attention towards education. Real time examples via visual mode would make it more easy and everlasting in the minds of the people.

➤ **Creating Digital Lessons**

It is very essential to be updated on the online tools and techniques to frame effective digital lessons. The educators must have a good acumen to use the digital tools. Regular up gradation of these skills would keep the educators on track. Colourful images, audio- visual aids, supporting documents on case studies, psychometric tools, powerpoints would enable digital lessons to be more interesting. Quizzes conducted through Edpuzzle, Kahoot sound highly interesting for the students.

➤ **Reviewing Policies**

Strict adherence to online safety policies, such as awareness on Cyber-bullying & e-safety are aspects that require concern. Therefore, online safety rules and policies, successful monitoring and evaluating processes must be adopted to ensure cyber safety.

➤ **Creating Digital Ambassadors**

Digital ambassadors can be easily identified among the students. The one who takes an active interest in learning new techniques via digital mode and is a source of inspiration will be the effective ambassador.

➤ **Conducting Webinars and E-Certificates**

By conducting and attending webinars, it helps students to gain lots of information and knowledge. It is also time consuming and initiate lots of opportunities. It indeed helps students to build relationships and contacts for their future development.

Moving towards better future:

After China, India has the second-largest school system in the world. the network of 1.5 million schools in the e-learning sector. As the leader of the digital revolution and a recognized multicultural and multilingual nation, India will undoubtedly benefit from the platforms that make e-learning the "new normal" as the nation develops.

CONCLUSION

Digitalization can be the new 'change' to bring in better transformation to the society. India is looking for a rapid growth in the field of education, and strongly believes to build a better future for the next generation. Thanks to the pandemic, COVID-19 has at least one positive impact, it is certainly the online education which is still motivating the young brains to study with hope, and envisage a better future. India sets a bigger step with the help of digitalization during the pandemic. This New normal indeed has proved that, amidst the distressful situations life can still be positive and lively. With the help of digitalisation, education was able to break all hurdles thus triggering a positive impact and in the minds of the people. Digitalisation has charted a vision and helped one to understand that, education plays a vital role during the global crisis and envisioning a path for nation building. 'The new normal' kind of digital education supports every community across the globe. India being a developing nation is stepping far ahead than other developing countries to reach education to every child in the society thus providing 'Education for All' under Article 21A of our fundamental rights. India marches ahead in the field of education through technology.

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